

Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome and its Homoeopathic Management: A Systematic Review

*Dr G Senthil Kumaran

PG Scholar, Dept. of Homoeopathic Pharmacy
GD Memorial Homoeopathic Medical College and Hospital
Patna, Bihar, India

Dr N Rajalakshmi

PG Scholar, Dept. of Rperatory
GD Memorial Homoeopathic Medical College and Hospital
Patna, Bihar, India.

Dr S Sandhya

Associate Professor, Dept. of Community Medicine
Venkateswara Homoeopathic Medical College and Hospital
Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India.

Dr V Divya

UG Scholar
Venkateswara Homoeopathic Medical College and Hospital,
Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India.

Abstract—Polycystic ovarian syndrome is a common endocrine disorder predominantly affecting women of reproductive age group. This is one of the major causes for infertility. The objective of this article is to conduct a review of the Research articles indexed in PUBMED and GOOGLE SCHOLAR regarding the effectiveness of Homeopathic treatment in PCOS. This review is done to analyse the research work done by various Homoeopathic colleges till date in the field of PCOS and future research required to be undertaken in this less explored area. Analysis of these studies unveil the management strategy for PCOS through homoeopathy. These includes publications of various Homoeopathic medical colleges from 1990-2022 published in Indian journal of homoeopathy, International Journal of health sciences and research, Materia Novum- The journal of homoeopathy. The publications pertaining to the clinical research work were included in the review. All publications are categorized as observational studies, clinical studies and case reports. Out of 12 publications searched, 4 were included in this article. Observational case studies and case series shows the improvement in the clinical symptoms, USG findings and in the quality of life of the patient. Therefore, these studies should be given importance in further homoeopathic research and should be authenticated with the pragmatic trials

Keywords—PCOS, Observational studies, case series, Homoeopathy.

INTRODUCTION

Polycystic ovarian syndrome is a common endocrine disorder predominantly affecting women of reproductive age group. It is one of the major causes for infertility. Across the world, 1 in every 10 women is diagnosed with PCOS. The WHO data suggests that approximately 3.4% of women affected by PCOS globally^[3]. It is important to improve the clinical and therapeutic management of PCOS patient. The three common factors associated with PCOS include anovulation, hyperandrogenism, cystic ovaries. It causes impairment in Quality of life with major impact on mental and physical health. Homoeopathy is the second widely used health care system according to WHO. Studies have shown that Homoeopathic treatment for PCOS was associated with a significant reduction in the use and costs of conventional drugs. One study, concluded that through Prospective observational study, it has been proved that Homoeopathic medicines are effective in the management of PCOS and improving the QOL of PCOS patient. Various Homoeopathic medical colleges have conducted several studies to evaluate the therapeutic usefulness of homoeopathic medicines in the management of PCOS. The objective of this review is to analyse the research work done by various Homoeopathic colleges till date in the field of PCOS and future research required to be undertaken in this less explored area. Analysis of these studies unveil the management strategy for PCOS through homoeopathy.

MATERIALS AND METHOD:

We collected PCOS-related publications of various Homoeopathic medical colleges from 1990-2022 published in Indian journal of homoeopathy, International Journal of health sciences and research, Materia Novum-The journal of homoeopathy. The publications pertaining to the clinical research work were included in the review. All publications are categorized as observational studies, clinical studies and case reports.

RESULT:

12 publications related to PCOS were included in this article. These publications consist of 4 observational study, 3 case series and 5 case reports. The results of 4 observational studies were briefly compiled in this article. The result of case series and case report of personal experience of clinicians were tabulated. Only the Case reports showed evidence-based improvement in the PCOS patient.

Table 1: Assessment tool used in the Study

S.No.	Author	Assessment tool used in the study
1	Chetna Deeplamba et.al [4]	PCOSQ scale Ferriman-Gallwey Visual scale
2	Priti Ashok.Malvekar et.al [1]	Ferriman-Gallwey Visual scale Acne Global severity scale
3	Girish Gupta et.al [6]	PCOSQ scale
4	Dr. R. Kundu et.al [5]	PCOSQ scale
5	Sonia Raizada [10]	Integrative Medicine Outcome scale
6	Dr.Poonam Meghani[7]	USG Findings
7	Rahul Singh [13]	USG Findings
8	Padmalaya Rath [9]	USG Findings
9	Arunava Nath et.al [8]	USG Findings
10	Vikram Saini [12]	USG Findings
11	Mehadi Arif Billah [2]	USG Findings
12	Bhuvaneswari Rajachandrasekar[11]	PCOSQ scale

SINGLE BLIND RANDOMISED PLACEBO-CONTROLLED PILOT STUDY CONDUCTED AT CENTRAL COUNCIL FOR RESEARCH IN HOMEOPATHY, DR. D. P. RASTOGI CENTRAL RESEARCH INSTITUTE, EXTENSION CENTRE OF DRUG STANDARDIZATION UNIT, PRINCESS DURRU SHEHVAR CHILDREN'S AND GENERAL HOSPITAL.

This is a Single Blind randomised placebo- controlled pilot study. 60 cases collected where 30 cases in verum group and 30 cases in placebo group. The study period was 6months. The primary objective was to show the regular menstrual cycle along with improvement in either ultrasonography or hirsutism/acne. The secondary outcome was to evaluate the improvement in QOL using PCOSQ scale. Follow-ups made in the interval of one month. Remedies were selected based on the symptom totality. Modified Ferriman–Gallwey visual scoring method was used as a scale for hirsutism, acne global severity scale for acne and PCOSQ scale for measuring the QOL of PCOS patient. The remedies given were *Pulsatilla nigricans*, *Natrum muriaticum*, *Sepia officinalis*, *Calcarea carbonica*, *Lycopodium clavatum*, *Phosphorus*, *China*, *Nux vomica* and *Sulphur*. 23 cases required single medicines and the change of medicine needed for 7 cases. Improvement status of patient in menstrual regularity in homoeopathic intervention is 60% Improvement status of patient in menstrual regularity in control group is none. The selection bias and ascertainment bias due to nonblinding and lack of allocation concealment couldn't be avoided in this study. Trial limitations include the shorter duration of follow-up in the assessment of regular menstrual cycle and changes in USG finding. Vitamin D deficiency can be an effective factor in the development of PCOS and Vitamin D supplementation helps in prevention of this condition and which was not evaluated.

A PROSPECTIVE OBSERVATIONAL STUDIES DONE AT MOTIWALA HOMOEOPATHIC COLLEGE AND HOSPITAL AND PERIPHERAL OPDs:

This study conducted on 45 female patients with the known condition – PCOS. The diagnosis made based on ROTTERDAM CRITERIA 2003: oligomenorrhoea and/or anovulation, hyperandrogenism and USG report with poly ovarian cysts. PCOSQ scale used to measure

the improvement in the quality of life of woman with PCOS. Their primary objective is to evaluate the effectiveness of homoeopathic medicine in the management of PCOS and secondary objective is to measure the changes in the quality of life of woman with PCOS using PCOSQ scale. Clinical investigations like thyroid profile test, hormonal profile test was not included. The study period was about 6months. The medicines were selected based on symptom totality and repertorized using computer repertory RADAR. Measurement of PCOSQ was done at first and last follow up. Medicines like *Natrum muriaticum*, *Pulsatilla nigricans*, *Lycopodium clavatum*, *Thyroidinum* are given based on repertorization. Out of 45 cases, 40 cases showed improvement and 5 cases not improved. 88.8% of patients showed improvement in health-related quality of life and 11.1% of patients not showed any improvement. This study concludes that homoeopathic medicines are effective in management of PCOS and in improving the QOL of PCOS patients.

A CLINICAL STUDY DONE AT BHARATI VIDHYAPEETH MEDICAL FOUNDATION HOMOEOPATHIC HOSPITAL, PERIPHERAL OPDs AND VARIOUS URBAN AND RURAL CAMP SERIES:

This study conducted on 30 female patients with the known condition – PCOS. The patient selected based on ROTTERDAM CRITERIA 2003 as per American society of reproductive medicine and European society of human reproduction and embryology guidelines. Female aged between 12- 45 years are included. Clinical evidence of hirsutism (Ferriman score 8 and above) and acne (acne global severity scale 1 and above) were included. Other investigations like thyroid profile test and hormonal profile test were not included. The study period was 25 weeks. The remedy was selected based on totality of symptoms. According to this study, the maximum prevalence was noticed in the age group 20-25 years.

The clinical presentation varies:

1. Irregular menses once in 30-45 days was present in 8 cases (26.66%),
2. Irregular menses once in 45 – 55 days was present in 19 cases (63.34%)
3. Irregular menses once in 55-65 days was present in 03 cases (10%)
4. Amenorrhea was present in 3 cases (10%)

5. Weight gain was present in 4 cases (13.33%),
6. Hirsutism was present in 2 cases (6.66%),
7. Acne present in 26 cases (86.67%),
8. Scanty menstrual flow was noticed in 6 cases (20%),
9. Profuse flow of menses in 2 cases (6.66%).

Constitutional medicines like *Natrum muriaticum*, *Pulsatilla nigricans*, *Lycopodium clavatum*, *Calcarea carbonicum*, *Phosphorus*, *Borax*, *Graphitis*, *Sepia officinalis*, *Kalium phosphoricum* were selected based on totality of symptoms. All 30 patients received anti-miasmatic treatment as inter current remedy.

Improvement status of the patient: Out of 30 cases:

- a. Excellent response: 8 patients
- b. good response: 4 patients
- c. moderate response: 4 patients
- d. mild response: 10 patients
- e. poor response: 2 patients

This study concluded that constitutional treatment along with anti-miasmatic remedy gives significant improvement in treating PCOS patients.

PROSPECTIVE OBSERVATIONAL STUDY CONDUCTED AT HOMOEOPATHIC RESEARCH FOUNDATION, LUCKNOW:

This study conducted on 38 female patients aged between 18- 40years, diagnosed PCOS with the evidence of USG abdomen. The study period was 24 months. The primary outcome was to measure the overall quality of life (QOL) using PCOS Questionnaire. The secondary outcome was to measure the changes in hormonal, profiles and USG findings. Post-treatment hormonal profile, biochemical parameters such as lipid profile, fasting blood sugar, Homeostatic Model Assessment of Insulin Resistance (Hom IR) levels, biological markers for PCOS were not included. The remedy was selected based on the symptom totality. Repertorization was done by using 'Homopath Classic' software (Version 8.0) (Mind Technologies Private Limited, Mumbai, Maharashtra, India). All prescription started with 30th potency and increased according to the need of the case. Out of 38 cases, 4 cases not appeared for followup and those were excluded. The most prescribed medicines were *Calcarea carbonicum*(38.24%) and *Lycopodium clavatum*(26.47%) accounting to 64.71% of the total medicines. This study shows the positive effect of homoeopathic medicines in the treatment of PCOS.

Table 2: STUDY OF EFFECTIVENESS OF HOMOEOPATHIC MEDICINES IN POLYCYSTIC OVARIAN SYNDROME PUBLISHED BY VARIOUS HOMOEOPATHIC MEDICAL COLLEGES IN INDIA

AUTHOR	PUBLISHED TITLE	DESIGN	PATIENTS	SUMMARY OF RESULTS		OBSERVATIONS
				IMPROVEMENT STATUS OF THE PATIENTS	ROLE OF HOMOEOPATHY	
Chetna Deepplamba[4] Praveen Oberai Raj.k.Manchanda Padmalaya Rath P. Hima Bindu Maya Padmanabhan	Evaluation of homoeopathic treatment in polycystic ovary syndrome: A single-blind, randomised, placebo-controlled pilot study	Single Blind randomised placebo-controlled pilot study conducted at 1. Central Council for Research in Homeopathy, New Delhi, India 2. DR. D. P. Rastogi Central Research Institute (H), Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India 3. Extension Centre of Drug Standardization Unit, Princess Durru Shehvar Children's and General Hospital, Hyderabad, Telangana, India Duration of study: February 2014 to May 2015	60 cases enrolled 30 cases in verum 30 cases in placebo group	Improvement status of patient in menstrual regularity in homoeopathic intervention: 60% Improvement status of patient in menstrual regularity in control group: None	<i>Pulsatilla nigricans</i> (n = 12), <i>Natrum muriaticum</i> (n = 4), <i>Sepia officinalis</i> (n = 3), <i>Calcarea carbonica</i> (n = 3), <i>Lycopodium clavatum</i> (n = 3), <i>Phosphorus</i> (n = 2), <i>China</i> (n = 1), <i>Nux vomica</i> (n = 1) and <i>Sulphur</i> (n = 1). The single medicine was given to 23 cases and 7 cases required the change of medicine	Homoeopathic intervention along with LSM has shown promising outcome; further comparative study with standard conventional treatment on adequate sample size is desirable.
Priti Ashok.Malvekar[1] Sameer S. Nadgauda Arun Bhargav Jadhav	A Clinical study to see the Effect of Homoeopathic Medicines in Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome of Reproductive age group between 12-45 years.	Single arm, clinical study conducted at Bharati Vidhyapeeth Medical foundation's Homoeopathic hospital, peripheral OPDs and various urban and rural camp series Duration of study: 25 weeks	30 patients	Improvement status of the patient: a. Excellent response: 8 patients b. good response: 4 patients c. moderate response: 4 patients d. mild response: 10 patients e. poor response: 2 patients 1.Improvement showed in irregular menses: 14 cases 2. Improvement showed in complaints of acne: 21 cases 3. Improvement showed in Health-Related Quality of Life: 25 cases	Indicated constitutional medicines: <i>Natrum muriaticum</i> <i>Lycopodium clavatum</i> <i>Pulsatilla nigricans</i> <i>Calcarea carbonicum</i> <i>Phosphorus</i> <i>Borax</i> <i>Graphitis</i> <i>Sepia officinalis</i>	Lifestyle modification along with homoeopathic treatment is effective in reducing signs and symptoms of PCOS.
Girish Gupta[6] Naveen Gupta Santhosh Singh Varanasi Roja Deepti Dewan	Homoeopathic treatment of women with polycystic ovarian syndrome: A prospective observational study	Prospective observational study Conducted at homoeopathic Research Foundation, Lucknow. Duration of study: July 2015 to June 2017	80 cases screened 38 cases fulfilling eligibility criteria 18 patients completed follow ups of 12 months.	Improvement status of patient: Out of 38 cases 34 cases showed significant improvement	The most prescribed medicines were <i>Calcarea carbonica</i> (38.24%) and <i>Lycopodium clavatum</i> . (26.47%) accounting to 64.71% of the total medicines	The study gives positive leads in the management of PCOS with Homoeopathic medicines. The changes were observed in PCOS questionnaire (PCOSQ), hormonal profile and USG.
Dr. R. Kundu[5] Dr. Suhail sheikh Dr. Vishal nimbhore Dr. Varsha dharne Dr. Shweta Patil Dr. Sonali Roham Ms. Ketki Chaudhari Ms. Taba Ansari Ms. Fouzia siddiqui	Evaluation of the effectiveness of homoeopathic medicine in the management of polycystic ovarian syndrome: A Prospective observational study.	Prospective observational study conducted at Motiwala Homoeopathic Medical College and Hospital and Peripheral OPDs Duration of study: 6months	45 patients enrolled.	1.Improvement status of the patient: a. 40 patients showed improvement b. 5 patients didn't show any improvement. 2. Improvement in Health-Related Quality of Life: a. 88.88% of patients showed improvement. b. 11.11% of patients didn't show any improvement	Frequently indicated medicines: <i>Natrum muriaticum</i> <i>Pulsatilla nigricans</i> <i>Calcarea carbonicum</i> <i>Lycopodium clavatum</i> <i>Aurum muriaticum natrum</i> <i>Thyroidinum</i> <i>Calcarea fluoricum</i>	Homoeopathic medicines showed are effective in improving the health-Related Quality of Life of PCOS patients.

Table 3: SUMMARY OF PERSONAL EXPERIENCE OF CLINICIANS

S.NO	AUTHOR	PUBLISHED TITLE	REMEDIES FOUND USEFUL	INDICATIONS
1.	Sonia Raizada[10]	Homoeopathic management of polycystic ovarian syndrome – A case series	<i>Natrum muriaticum</i> <i>Calcarea carbonicum</i> <i>Silicea terra</i> <i>Pulsatilla nigricans</i> <i>Lycopodium clavatum</i> <i>Sepia officinalis</i>	<i>Natrum muriaticum</i> : patient's constitutional make-up, like tendency to catch cold easily, tendency to develop urticaria, irregular and profuse menses and hot patient. <i>Calcarea carbonicum</i> : tendency to catch cold easily. desire for eggs, sweets and cold drinks. sleep lying on her abdomen. mouth remained open while sleeping. ambithermal. does not express herself when angry and used to weep when alone. liked to be consoled. Fear of being alone, of height, water and electricity and desired company. <i>Silicea terra</i> : delayed menses, constipation before and during menses, desire for milk, offensive perspiration, talking during sleep and getting angered easily. <i>Pulsatilla nigricans</i> : hot thermal inclination, decreased thirst, desire for fatty food and consolation ameliorates <i>Lycopodium clavatum</i> : desire for sweets, liking for warm food, hard, unsatisfactory stools <i>Sepia officinalis</i> : Perspiration was cold, more on the scalp, even during sleep and stained the linen yellow. irritability and aggravation from consolation
2.	Dr. Poonam Meghani[7]	Efficacy of Homoeopathy in PCOS: An Evidence Based Case Study	<i>Calcarea carbonicum</i>	<i>Calcarea carbonicum</i> : A/F disappointment of love , Irritable on trifles , Taciturn , Aversion to company , Weeps or broods when alone,thirstless ,craving for salt and also likes pastry & chocolates , Constipation without urge for evacuation since last 9 months , Irregular, scanty menses followed by delayed menses Severe cramping pain starts from lower abdomen extending to back and lower extremities
3.	Rahul Singh[13]	Evidence Based Treatment of Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome/Diseases (PCOS/PCOD) with Homoeopathy	<i>Pulsatilla nigricans</i> <i>Calcarea carbonicum</i>	<i>Pulsatilla nigricans</i> : Craving: Pickle. Thirst: Below average. Perspiration: only on exertion. Thermal: Hot, can't remain in a warm room, likes open air. Stool: Regular, Disturbed by oily and fast food. Get irritable on small thing. Weeping mood. <i>Calcarea carbonicum</i> : Craving: Spicy food and non-veg. Perspiration: Profuse, mainly on head. Hair fall, obesity and indigestion. Lack of confidence. Yielding in nature, friendly.
4.	Padmalaya Rath[9]	Management of PCOS through Homoeopathy-A case report	<i>Calcarea carbonicum</i>	<i>Calcarea carbonicum</i> : Chilly patient, tendency to catch cold, tonsil involvement since childhood, desire for egg, constipation, soreness of breast before and during menses and amelioration after menses, leucorrhoea thin milky white and tendency to gain weight.
5.	Arunava Nath[8] Deb Kumar Palit Nivedita Kundu	Homoeopathic management of ovarian cyst – a case report	<i>Lycopodium clavatum</i>	<i>Lycopodium clavatum</i> : Intellectual person, Calm and quiet disposition, she loved company, Hot thermal reaction, Desire for sweets and warm food, Pain in right side of lower abdomen before and during menses, Pain in right side of abdomen, Constipation during menses, Profuse and offensive perspiration, right sided ovarian cyst
6.	Vikram Saini[12]	Homoeopathy in polycystic ovarian disease: A case study	<i>Natrum muriaticum</i>	MIND - AILMENTS FROM - love; disappointed MIND - ANXIETY - health; about - own health; one's MIND - CONSOLATION - agg. MIND - DISCONTENTED - reserved displeasure MIND - FEAR - cancer; of GENERALS - FOOD and DRINKS - sweets – aversion
7.	Mehadi Arif Billah[2], Abdul Hakim Sk, Vignesh kumar S	Management of Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome (PCOS) with Constitutional Homoeopathic Medicine- a Case report	<i>Lycopodium clavatum</i>	<i>Lycopodium clavatum</i> : Mind-dullness Mind-sluggishness Stomach-desires-sour foods Stomach-disordered -fat foods Female genitalia -leucorrhoea –menses--after Head-pain –menses --before

TABLE 3: SUMMARY OF PERSONAL EXPERIENCE OF CLINICIAN's (contd.)

S.NO	AUTHOR	PUBLISHED TITLE	REMEDIES FOUND USEFUL	INDICATIONS
8.	Bhuvanewari Rajachandrasekar[11] Nilina P Ravindran	Usefulness of Homoeopathic medicines in polycystic ovarian syndrome-Case series	<p>Case 1: Initially started with <i>Natrum muriaticum</i> later <i>Lycopodium clavatum</i> given.</p> <p>Case 2.: Initially started with <i>Lachesis</i> later <i>Lycopodium clavatum</i> Given.</p> <p>Case 3: Initially started with <i>Calcarea carbonicum</i> later <i>Pulsatilla nigricans</i> given.</p>	<p>Totality of symptoms: Suppressed emotions. No sexual satisfaction. Pain in the breast before menses. Scanty menses. Abdomen distension.>flatus Reportorial result: natrum muriaticum – 16/6 lycopodium clavatum – 16/6 7months condition cured</p> <p>Totality of symptoms: Anxious about her disease. Haemorrhoids during menses. Headache increased by mental exertion and at night. Menses is irregular, profuse, protracted and clotted. Reportorial result: Lachesis: 19/7 Lycopodium clavatum: 18/7 18 months condition cured</p> <p>Totality of symptoms: Thirst-reduced,she prefers cold drinks. Desires eggLeucorrhoea before and after menses. Headache before menses. Tendency to obesity Reportorial result: Calcarea carbonicum- 18/6 Phosphorus- 18/6 Pulsatilla nigricans- 18/6 12 months condition cured</p>

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

People around the world go for Homoeopathic treatment because of the following reason: it is effective in treating long-standing chronic disease, gives permanent cure by treating the disease from the root, safe and free from side effects. It is cost effective which is one of the reason for opting Homoeopathic medicines in developing countries. In India, Homoeopathic treatment has high acceptability rate. The homoeopaths are aware of treating the sick rather than the disease condition. Along with lifestyle modifications, the individualized Homoeopathic treatment, gives permanent relief. Many Homoeopathic colleges in India, conducted various studies to find the efficacy of homoeopathic remedies in treating PCOS condition. In this article, 12 publications regarding PCOS- Homoeopathic treatment were reviewed and came to a conclusion that in clinical trials investigations were not included in the assessment of the disease condition instead PCOSQ scale, Ferriman scale,

Acne global severity scale were used for the evaluation of quality of life of the patient, hirsutisim, acne respectively during the disease condition which reduces the evidence based improvement in the pathological changes of the condition. Case reports show evidence based improvement in the condition. Therefore in future clinical trials, in-vitro studies should be conducted. Investigations like USG findings, hormonal assays are required to assess the Homoeopathic Management in PCOS cases during the clinical trial.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We are thankful to Dr.A.Sakuntala M.D (HOM), Correspondent / Principal, Venkateswara Homoeopathic Medical College and Hospital, for their advice, encouragement and continuous support in this study. The research department of Venkateshwara Homoeopathic Medical College and Hospital, Chennai. Special thanks to the professors and heads of the department.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST:

There are no conflicts of interest.

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